

TRPV1 modulation associated with reduced thermal hyperalgesia following vitamin D₃ supplementation in gabapentin-treated neuropathic pain rats

Annette d'Arqom^{1,2*}, Hajar Mar'atussolikah Supriyanto^{3*}, Asyirah Mujahidah Fillah⁴,
Mohammad Fathul Qorib^{1,2}, Rimbun^{1,2}, Ming Tatt Lee⁵, Sharifah Zamiah Syed Abdul Kadir⁶

1 Department of Anatomy, Histology, Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya, Indonesia

2 Molecular and Biomedical Science Research Group, Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya, Indonesia

3 Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Muhammadiyah Kalimantan Timur, Samarinda, Indonesia

4 Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Darussalam Gontor, Ponorogo, Indonesia

5 Office of Postgraduate Studies, UCSI University, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

6 Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine, Universiti Malaya, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

Corresponding author: Annette d'Arqom (annette-d-a@fk.unair.ac.id)

Received 28 November 2025 ♦ Accepted 25 May 2026 ♦ Published 5 June 2026

Citation: d'Arqom A, Supriyanto HM, Fillah AM, Qorib MF, Rimbun, Lee MT, Kadir SZSA (2026) TRPV1 modulation associated with reduced thermal hyperalgesia following vitamin D₃ supplementation in gabapentin-treated neuropathic pain rats. *Pharmacia* 73: e180741. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e180741>

Abstract

Neuropathic pain (NeuP), defined as pain arising from lesions or disease of the somatosensory system, remains difficult to manage due to limited treatment efficacy and frequent side effects. As a neurosteroid with anti-inflammatory properties, vitamin D₃ may offer additional benefits in NeuP therapy. This study evaluated the effectiveness of combining vitamin D₃ with gabapentin in a rat model of chronic constriction injury (CCI). Adult Wistar rats were assigned to seven groups: normal, sham, negative control (CCI), positive control (gabapentin), and three intervention groups receiving gabapentin plus vitamin D₃ at 500, 1,000, or 4,000 IU for 28 days. Combination therapy significantly reduced hyperalgesia ($p < 0.05$), but not allodynia, in a dose-dependent manner, which corresponded with decreased transient receptor potential vanilloid 1 (TRPV1) expression in peripheral nerves. Gabapentin alone and combination therapy reduced inflammatory cell infiltration. These findings suggest that vitamin D₃ supplementation in gabapentin-treated rats was associated with improved antihyperalgesic outcomes, possibly through TRPV1 modulation.

Keywords

cholecalciferol, chronic pain, gabapentinoid, neuropathic pain, noncommunicable diseases, pain management

* These authors contributed equally to this work.

Introduction

The International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP) defines neuropathic pain (NeuP) as “*pain arising as a direct consequence of a lesion or disease affecting the somatosensory system*” (IASP 2025). This condition results from nerve damage that disrupts excitability, leading to hyperexcitability in the injured nerves and their surrounding healthy counterparts (Thacker et al. 2007). In the UK, 9.2% of adults experience NeuP with a variety of underlying etiologies (Baskozos et al. 2023), while in Germany, it is reported in 37% of patients presenting with low back pain (Freynhagen et al. 2006) and affects 2.8% of the Chinese population (Li et al. 2018). The persistent nature of this pain negatively impacts patients’ well-being (Baskozos et al. 2023).

The pathophysiology of NeuP is initiated by nerve tissue injury that triggers inflammation, oxidative stress, and the activation of microglia. This damage releases inflammatory mediators such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6, and PGE₂, which cause neuroinflammation. This state promotes an increased influx of Na⁺ and Ca²⁺ ions into peripheral nerve fibers (Finnerup et al. 2021). The significant rise in intracellular Ca²⁺ concentration is associated with the activation of numerous transient receptor potential vanilloid 1 (TRPV1) receptors that are expressed by axons (Frey et al. 2018) and also Schwann cells (Grüter et al. 2020). This activation, in turn, triggers the release of glutamate into the synaptic membrane (Malek et al. 2015). Excessive glutamate release causes hyperexcitability in signal transmission to the brain, leading to hyperalgesia and allodynia, which are common symptoms of NeuP (Alles and Smith 2018). Hyperalgesia is an exaggerated pain response to a noxious stimulus, stemming from the sensitization of peripheral nociceptors. In contrast, allodynia is the perception of pain from a normally non-painful stimulus, resulting from central sensitization and aberrant processing in the central nervous system (den Boer et al. 2019). It is noteworthy that TRPV1 activation in axons is involved in the pain response (Gao et al. 2024), while its activation in Schwann cells is associated with nerve regeneration (Zakir et al. 2012).

Managing NeuP is challenging because current treatments often have limited efficacy and significant side effects. A multimodal approach is therefore often used, combining different classes of drugs, such as analgesics, antidepressants, opioids, and anticonvulsants, to improve therapeutic results while reducing adverse effects (Kaye et al. 2025). Gabapentin has been endorsed as a first-line agent for the treatment of NeuP (Finnerup et al. 2021). However, a meta-analysis study concluded that the effectiveness of gabapentin in reducing NeuP was 30–40%, while the remaining patients experienced side effects but no pain relief (Wiffen et al. 2017). Thus, further investigation is needed into other potential adjuvant agents that may exhibit anti-inflammatory, antinociceptive, and antioxidant properties to more effectively treat NeuP with fewer adverse effects (Kaye et al. 2025).

Vitamin D₃ has emerged as a prominent micronutrient in pain management. While its primary function is the regulation of calcium and phosphate homeostasis, its mechanism of action is more complex. Murine studies show that vitamin D₃ directly influences the development of neuropathic pain by promoting axonogenesis and improving the sensory response of peripheral nerve tissue (Chabas et al. 2013). Interestingly, an *in vitro* study shows that vitamin D₃ is a partial agonist of the TRPV1 receptor (Long et al. 2020). This study will investigate how vitamin D₃ affects gabapentin’s ability to reduce neuropathic pain behaviors, such as hyperalgesia and allodynia. Furthermore, the underlying mechanisms will be investigated by examining TRPV1 expression and inflammatory cell infiltration in the affected sciatic nerves.

Materials and methods

Animals

Thirty-five adult male *Rattus norvegicus* (16–20 weeks, 200–300 g) were obtained from Kampung Mitra (Jombang, Indonesia) and maintained in the animal facility of the Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Airlangga. Rats were maintained in a 12:12 light cycle and were given *ad libitum* access to water and food. All rats were acclimatized for 2 weeks before the intervention. Animal procedures were approved by the Ethics Committee No. 243/EC/KEPK/FKUA/2023 and followed the ARRIVE guidelines for reporting animal research. Rats exhibiting motor defects, signs of illness, or death were excluded from the study. The sample size was calculated using the Federer formula, requiring a minimum of four rats per group. An extra rat was added to each group as a reserve. Rats were randomly assigned to seven groups: a control group (no intervention), a sham group (surgery without nerve ligation), a negative control group (surgery with nerve ligation), and a positive control group (surgery with nerve ligation followed by 28 days of gabapentin). Three intervention groups received surgery with nerve ligation and a combination of gabapentin and vitamin D₃ (500, 1,000, or 4,000 IU) for 28 days. Treatment for all surgical groups began 7 days post-ligation. All rats were sacrificed on day 35, and the sciatic nerves were isolated for analysis (Fig. 1a). During the experimental period, five rats died and were excluded, resulting in 28 rats included in the final analysis ($n = 4$ per group).

Neuropathic pain induction

NeuP was induced by chronic constriction injury (CCI) under aseptic conditions and intraperitoneal anesthesia cocktail (ketamine 100 mg/mL and xylazine 20 mg/mL, 8 mL/kg BW). Briefly, after antiseptic procedures, a 1.5 cm longitudinal incision was made parallel to the vertebra, positioned 0.5 cm caudal to the pelvis. The biceps femoris and gluteus superficialis muscles were then

Figure 1. a. Timeline of procedures; b. Ligation of the sciatic nerve to induce neuropathic pain.

bluntly dissected to expose the sciatic nerve. The nerve was isolated, and two ligatures were placed using 4-0 chromic catgut suture, spaced 1 mm apart (Fig. 1b). Following ligation, the surgical wound was closed in layers, and a topical antibiotic was administered. Significant manifestations of NeuP were observed within 7 days post-ligation (Jaggi et al. 2011). For the sham group, the same surgical procedure was performed, including nerve exposure, but without ligation.

Pain evaluation

Pain was assessed by measuring hyperalgesia and allodynia, performed by two independent researchers blinded to the treatment groups. Hyperalgesia, or sensitivity to heat, was evaluated using a hot plate (51 °C). Thermal withdrawal latency (TWL) was recorded until the rat exhibited a withdrawal response, such as paw licking, jumping, or flicking. To prevent potential tissue damage, a maximum cutoff time of 30 s was enforced for all measurements (Tu et al. 2012). Each animal was tested in triplicate with 5-min intertrial intervals, and the mean TWL was calculated. Allodynia was assessed by measuring the paw withdrawal threshold (PWT) using the up-down method with von Frey filaments applied to the plantar surface of the hind paws (Chaplan et al. 1994). Briefly, rats were placed on a wire mesh, and their hind paws were stimulated. A paw withdrawal, flicking, or licking response was considered positive. The force of the filament was adjusted based on the response, and rats were classified as having allodynia if they responded to a filament exerting a force of less than 4 g (Reyes-García et al. 2004).

Chemicals

For a period of 28 days, both vitamin D₃ (cholecalciferol, Cayman Chemical, Sapphire Bioscience Pty. Ltd., Australia) and gabapentin (Xi'an Faithful Biological Technology Co. Ltd., China) were administered to the subjects orally on a daily basis. Vitamin D₃ was initially dissolved in ethanol and then deionized water to create working solutions of 12.5, 25, and 100 µg/mL, corresponding to 500, 1,000, and 4,000 IU. Gabapentin was prepared daily by diluting

a 15 mg/mL solution with deionized water for a final oral dose of 60 mg/kg BW (Câmara et al. 2015). The selected doses were chosen based on previously reported effective ranges in pain research (Chabas et al. 2013; Gendelman et al. 2015; Poisbeau et al. 2019).

Evaluation of nerve inflammation

After euthanasia, the sciatic nerve was excised from the posterior thigh. The harvested nerve segments were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin for 48 h, followed by dehydration and clearing. After embedding, tissue was sectioned (5–6 µm) and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E). Inflammatory cells, including neutrophils (characterized by lobulated nuclei and pale cytoplasm) and lymphocytes (small cells with a dense, round nucleus and minimal cytoplasm), were quantified. Five non-overlapping fields per section were selected using a systematic sampling approach, starting from a predefined reference point and proceeding in a fixed pattern across the tissue to minimize selection bias. Areas with tissue damage or staining artifacts were excluded. Cell counting was performed manually using ImageJ software based on morphological criteria. Quantification was conducted in a blinded manner with respect to treatment groups. The average number of inflammatory cells per field was calculated for each sample and compared across groups.

Evaluation of TRPV1 receptor expression

Immunohistochemistry was performed on sciatic nerve sections to analyze TRPV1 expression. Briefly, blocks were cut into 5–6 µm-thick sections, mounted on glass slides, and incubated at 40 °C overnight. After deparaffinization and rehydration, antigen retrieval was performed, and endogenous peroxidase activity was blocked. Sections were incubated with a polyclonal TRPV1 antibody (Biorbyt Ltd., Cambridge, UK), followed by a primary antibody enhancer and a streptavidin–peroxidase detection system. A chromogen was applied for visualization, and Mayer's hematoxylin counterstain was used. For quantitative analysis, images were captured using a light microscope at 1,000× magnification. Five non-overlapping fields of

view were selected per section using a systematic sampling approach, starting from a predefined reference point and moving in a fixed pattern across the tissue to minimize selection bias. Areas with obvious tissue damage or staining artifacts were excluded. TRPV1 expression was quantified using the immunoreactivity score (IRS), calculated by multiplying the staining intensity score by the percentage of positive cells. Staining intensity was scored as 0 (no staining), 1 (weak), 2 (moderate), or 3 (strong), while the proportion of positive cells was categorized as 0 (no staining), 1 (<10%), 2 (10–50%), 3 (51–80%), and 4 (>80%). One representative section per animal was analyzed, and five non-overlapping fields were evaluated at 1,000 \times magnification. Image acquisition and scoring were performed blinded to the treatment groups. Quantification was conducted independently by two observers, and discrepancies were resolved by joint review to reach consensus. Positive staining was defined as distinct brown cytoplasmic or membranous chromogen deposition exceeding the background staining observed in negative control sections. All microscopy images were acquired using identical microscope settings.

Data analysis

The collected data were analyzed using GraphPad Prism 5.0 (California, USA). To determine whether there were significant differences between groups regarding the effect of vitamin D₃ as a potential combination therapy with gabapentin on NeuP, inflammatory cell counts, and TRPV1 receptor expression, a one-way ANOVA test followed by a *post hoc* test was performed. Behavioral data were analyzed using two-way repeated-measures ANOVA, with treatment group as the between-subject factor and time as the within-subject factor. Bonferroni *post hoc* tests were used for multiple comparisons ($p < 0.05$). Data were presented as mean \pm SD from $n = 4$. Correlations between parameters were analyzed using Pearson's correlation (r),

where 0.00–0.39 indicates a weak correlation, 0.40–0.59 indicates a moderate correlation, and ≥ 0.60 indicates a strong correlation (Schober et al. 2018). A result was considered statistically significant between groups if $p < 0.05$.

Results

Vitamin D₃ supplementation is associated with the pain-reducing effects of gabapentin

All analyses were conducted using 28 rats ($n = 4$ per group). To determine the effect of adjuvant vitamin D₃ on the pain-reducing effects of gabapentin (GBP), TWL was performed to evaluate hyperalgesia, and PWT was performed to evaluate allodynia induced by CCI. All groups appeared to have relatively similar observation times, with minor variations before CCI procedures. However, a significant decrease in TWL was noted post-CCI in the procedural groups compared to the normal group. This indicates that the NeuP model was successful, as there was an increase in pain sensitivity following injury. Notably, GBP treatment did not significantly alleviate hyperalgesia during 28 days of treatment. Interestingly, vitamin D₃ supplementation significantly increased the withdrawal time, suggesting that vitamin D₃ supplementation may reduce NeuP. The higher dose (4,000 IU) of vitamin D₃ began to reduce pain on day 14 ($p < 0.01$) of treatment, while the lower dose (1,000 IU) required a longer duration to produce an effect ($p < 0.05$, Fig. 2a).

Interestingly, although improvement in hyperalgesia was observed, no improvement was observed in allodynia. The PWT measurements taken before the CCI procedure showed relatively uniform values across all groups, with a range of 7–8.5 g and an average of 7.8 g. Following CCI induction, a decrease in PWT was observed in all groups except the normal control group. However, although an

Figure 2. Effects of gabapentin and vitamin D₃ on neuropathic pain behavior. **a.** Thermal withdrawal latency (TWL) representing thermal hyperalgesia. **b.** Paw withdrawal threshold (PWT) representing mechanical allodynia. Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 4$). # $p < 0.05$ and ### $p < 0.001$ vs. CCI group; * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ vs. GBP group. D0: baseline; D7: 7 days after CCI; D14–D35: treatment with gabapentin alone or combined with vitamin D₃. Statistical analysis was performed using two-way repeated-measures ANOVA followed by Bonferroni *post hoc* test.

increase in PWT was observed in the GBP and GBP + VD groups during the recovery phase, the differences were not statistically significant. A similar finding was also observed in GBP + VD, which gave a higher PWT than GBP alone ($p > 0.05$, Fig. 2b).

Effect of vitamin D₃ supplementation on nerve inflammation

A one-way ANOVA test was performed. The result indicated a significant difference in the number of inflammatory cells among the different treatment groups ($p < 0.001$). To identify the optimal therapeutic group for reducing the inflammatory cell count, a *post hoc* test was performed. As expected, the highest number of inflamma-

tory cells occurred in the CCI group, suggesting that the CCI procedure induced an inflammatory process, which is a known contributor to the development of NeuP. Interestingly, all gabapentin-treated groups, with or without vitamin D₃, exhibited a significant reduction compared to the CCI group ($p < 0.001$). Vitamin D₃ supplementation, at all doses, did not augment the anti-inflammatory effect of gabapentin (Fig. 3).

Effect of vitamin D₃ supplementation on TRPV1 expression

Using immunohistochemistry, TRPV1 expression was measured. Visual differences in TRPV1 receptor expression were determined by counting the number of recep-

Figure 3. Neuroinflammation of the sciatic nerve was analyzed using hematoxylin and eosin staining of nerve cross-sections under a microscope at 1,000× magnification. **a.** Normal; **b.** Sham; **c.** CCI; **d.** Gabapentin; **e.** Gabapentin + vitamin D₃ 500 IU; **f.** Gabapentin + vitamin D₃ 1,000 IU; **g.** Gabapentin + vitamin D₃ 4,000 IU; **h.** Number of inflammatory cells (neutrophils and lymphocytes). Data are presented as mean ± SD ($n = 4$). ### $p < 0.001$ vs. CCI group. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni *post hoc* test. The blue arrow indicates inflammatory cell infiltration; the yellow arrow indicates axons; the black arrow indicates Schwann cells.

tors on nerve axons and Schwann cells, which were visualized at 1,000× magnification using a light microscope. The examination showed differences in TRPV1 receptor expression between the treatment groups and the normal group. In both axons and Schwann cells, the TRPV1 receptor immunoreactive score (IRS) was lowest in the normal control group, serving as the study's baseline. Both the CCI and gabapentin monotherapy groups had the highest IRS scores, interpreted as “moderately positive” for TRPV1 expression. In contrast, all combination therapy groups—with varying doses of vitamin D₃—showed a significant dose-dependent decrease in their IRS scores, with results interpreted as “mildly positive.” The combination of gabapentin and vitamin D₃ yielded the lowest TRPV1

expression in Schwann cells in a dose-dependent manner ($p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, respectively, Fig. 4a–h). However, although a decreasing trend in TRPV1 expression in axons was observed, it was not statistically different (Fig. 4).

Correlation of inflammation, pain behavior, and TRPV1 receptor

Using Pearson's correlation, the results showed a strong negative correlation between immune cell infiltration and hyperalgesia ($r = -0.79$, $p < 0.001$, Fig. 5a), as well as with allodynia ($r = -0.66$, $p < 0.001$, Fig. 5b). Interestingly, immune cell presence was strongly positively correlated with the expression of the pain-related receptor TRPV1

Figure 4. TRPV1 receptor expression in the sciatic nerve under a microscope at 1,000× magnification. **a.** Normal; **b.** Sham; **c.** CCI; **d.** Gabapentin; **e.** Gabapentin + vitamin D₃ 500 IU; **f.** Gabapentin + vitamin D₃ 1,000 IU; **g.** Gabapentin + vitamin D₃ 4,000 IU; **h.** Distribution of mean IRS score values of TRPV1 receptor expression. Data are presented as mean ± SD ($n = 4$). # $p < 0.05$, ## $p < 0.01$, and ### $p < 0.001$ vs. CCI group; * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ vs. GBP group. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni *post hoc* test. The blue arrow indicates TRPV1-positive axons; the blue arrowhead indicates TRPV1-negative axons; the yellow arrow indicates TRPV1-positive Schwann cells; and the yellow arrowhead indicates TRPV1-negative Schwann cells.

Figure 5. Correlation of inflammation, pain behavior, and TRPV1 receptor. **a.** Correlation between hyperalgesia and inflammation; **b.** Correlation between allodynia and inflammation; **c.** Correlation between TRPV1 expression on Schwann cells and inflammation; **d.** Correlation between TRPV1 expression in axons and inflammation; **e.** Correlation between hyperalgesia and TRPV1 expression on Schwann cells; **f.** Correlation between allodynia and TRPV1 expression on Schwann cells.

on Schwann cells ($r = 0.64$, $p < 0.001$, Fig. 5c) and with the TRPV1 receptor in axons ($r = 0.41$, $p < 0.05$, Fig. 5d). Similar strong or moderate negative correlations were also found between TRPV1 receptors on Schwann cells and pain behavior, both hyperalgesia and allodynia ($r = -0.71$, $p < 0.001$ and $r = -0.59$, $p < 0.001$, respectively, Fig. 5e, f).

Discussion

The CCI animal model was chosen for this study because nerve trauma, which it simulates, is a common clinical cause of NeuP (Jaggi et al. 2011). This nerve constriction leads to edema and focal ischemia, causing infiltration of

inflammatory cells and an increase in pro-inflammatory cytokines (Cao et al. 2024). After a CCI procedure, the pain responses (hyperalgesia and allodynia) typically begin within 1 week and are most severe by the second week. These neuropathic pain symptoms can last for as long as 7 weeks (Castro et al. 2017). Increased expression of TRPV1 receptors (Malek et al. 2015) and decreased GABA signaling are observed after CCI (Fijałkowski et al. 2017).

Gabapentin works by modulating NMDA receptors, protein kinase C, and inflammatory cytokines to relieve pain (Kaye et al. 2025). Unfortunately, its side effects, including dizziness, somnolence, confusion, and peripheral edema, are drawbacks in its application (Wiffen et al. 2017). Vitamin D₃ was chosen as a supplementary therapy

because of its known relationship with NeuP. It is considered a promising treatment due to its role in various metabolic processes and its neurotropic properties, which are crucial for the maintenance and regeneration of peripheral nerves (Sari et al. 2020).

This study found that a combination of gabapentin and vitamin D₃ significantly reduced hyperalgesia, but not allodynia. This effect was consistent across all three tested doses of vitamin D₃ (500 IU, 1,000 IU, and 4,000 IU) when compared to gabapentin monotherapy. This result is plausible given the distinct pathophysiology of the two conditions. Hyperalgesia is primarily associated with peripheral sensitization and the overactivation of nociceptors, whereas allodynia is driven by central sensitization, where the central nervous system misinterprets non-painful signals (den Boer et al. 2019). Therefore, it is possible that vitamin D₃ exerts its effects through mechanisms that primarily target peripheral pathways or that different concentrations are required to influence central sensitization.

In this study, gabapentin at 60 mg/kg BW (equivalent to 600–700 mg in humans) did not significantly reduce hyperalgesia compared to the CCI group (Fig. 2A). Although gabapentin-treated animals showed numerically longer thermal withdrawal latency than the CCI group, the difference did not reach statistical significance. This contradicts some previous studies in rats that found gabapentin at a similar dose could alleviate NeuP pain symptoms (Câmara et al. 2015). Another *in vivo* study found that gabapentin 50 mg/kg BW did not reduce IL-6 and IL-10 production (Ismail et al. 2024). This inconsistency is also reflected in clinical practice, where a meta-analysis showed that less than 50% of patients experience pain relief even with much higher doses (1,800–3,600 mg) (Wiffen et al. 2017).

The lack of a significant change in allodynia suggests that neither gabapentin alone nor in combination with vitamin D₃ affected the central nervous system within the study's timeframe. This contrasts with a previous study where gabapentin (23 mg/kg BW) reduced allodynia, possibly due to a different type of neuropathic pain stimulation (Câmara et al. 2015). Clinical trials have shown that combining gabapentin (800–1,600 mg/day) with vitamin B can reduce pain in diabetic neuropathy, but the use of a visual analog scale (VAS) prevents the distinction between hyperalgesia and allodynia (Alvarado and Aguilar Navarro 2016). Prolonged observation or dose adjustment may be needed, since vitamin D₃ can act as a neurosteroid and modulate neuronal excitability and gene expression within the central nervous system (Shipton and Shipton 2015). This could help reverse the hyperexcitability that characterizes central sensitization and allodynia.

Although vitamin D₃ is known for its anti-inflammatory effects, this study found that it did not enhance gabapentin's anti-inflammatory capabilities. Gabapentin, while not a traditional anti-inflammatory drug, reduces neuroinflammation by binding to the $\alpha 2\delta$ subunit of voltage-gated calcium channels. This action modulates the release of pro-inflammatory neuropeptides and neu-

rotransmitters such as glutamate and substance P, thereby reducing the production of cytokines such as IL-6 and IL-8 (Yamaguchi et al. 2017). Some research also suggests that gabapentin inhibits the NF- κ B pathway and promotes the PPAR γ pathway (Rusciano 2024), which collectively reduces inflammation and sensitization in neuropathic pain.

Even though these findings did not support the anti-inflammatory effects of vitamin D₃, its role in modulating neuroinflammation in other ways could not be ruled out. Previous research suggests that vitamin D₃ indirectly reduces macrophages and other inflammatory cells by inhibiting the expression of Toll-like receptors on monocytes (Bishop et al. 2021). Low levels of vitamin D₃ are also linked to higher levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 in diabetic neuropathy (Xiaohua et al. 2021). Additionally, vitamin D₃ has been shown to reduce CD4 T-cell proliferation (Konijeti et al. 2016) and inhibit COX-2 (Wang et al. 2014) and prostaglandin production (Liu et al. 2014), all of which contribute to its anti-inflammatory effects.

This study found that gabapentin combined with vitamin D₃ (at doses of 500, 1,000, and 4,000 IU) significantly reduced TRPV1 receptor expression, especially in Schwann cells, and showed a greater reduction in TRPV1 expression compared with gabapentin alone (Fig. 4). The significant correlations between immune cell infiltration, pain behaviors, and TRPV1 expression provide a biological framework for understanding the therapeutic effects observed in this study. While gabapentin and vitamin D₃ did not enhance anti-inflammatory capabilities, their combined action on specific molecular targets is evident. The finding that combination therapy significantly reduced TRPV1 expression more effectively than gabapentin alone suggests that modulation of this receptor may contribute to the observed effects. This is particularly relevant given the strong positive correlation observed between immune cell presence and TRPV1 expression on Schwann cells, suggesting that the combination of gabapentin and vitamin D₃ may partly target this pathway. The reduction in TRPV1 expression may be associated with the improvement in hyperalgesia observed in the combination groups, even in the absence of a global reduction in inflammation.

This study demonstrated that the combination of gabapentin and vitamin D₃ produced a significant antihyperalgesic effect in rats with NeuP. The improvement was accompanied by a dose-dependent reduction in TRPV1 expression in Schwann cells, suggesting a possible peripheral mechanism for the observed behavioral outcomes. The results support previous evidence that vitamin D₃ possesses neuroprotective and anti-inflammatory properties and highlight its possible role as an adjuvant to gabapentin for neuropathic pain management. Although the mechanistic link between vitamin D₃ and TRPV1 modulation observed here is correlative, it provides a rationale for future studies focusing on causal signaling pathways.

Previous research has shown that TRPV1 expression increases in diabetic NeuP models (He et al. 2020), and that silencing the TRPV1 gene can alleviate pain by down-

regulating the CaMKII and ERK2 signaling pathways (Guo et al. 2019). This suggests that TRPV1 is a key component in the pathogenesis of NeuP and a potential therapeutic target. While TRPV1 is highly expressed in injured myelinated nerves, several studies have also demonstrated that TRPV1 expressed by Schwann cells is necessary for nerve regeneration and important for nerve function (Zakir et al. 2012). In this study, TRPV1 receptor expression was assessed at only one time point (35 days post-injury). At this stage, the acute inflammatory phase of nerve injury may have already declined, which could contribute to the lack of a significant difference in axonal TRPV1 expression. However, increased TRPV1 expression was still observed in Schwann cells, which may reflect ongoing regenerative processes following nerve injury.

Treatments for NeuP targeting various stages of the pain signaling pathway have been reviewed elsewhere (Kaye et al. 2025), including anti-inflammatory drugs (steroids and NSAIDs), local anesthetics, and centrally acting drugs such as gabapentin, antidepressants, and opioids. However, several limitations hinder the conclusion of this study. First, while the behavioral and immunohistochemistry assessments were performed independently by two blinded researchers, a fully randomized and double-blind design across all experimental steps would further reduce bias. Second, the absence of a vitamin D₃ monotherapy group limits the ability to determine whether vitamin D₃ alone exerts antinociceptive effects in this model. Therefore, the present study cannot distinguish whether the observed effect represents an additive, indirect, or potential adjuvant interaction with gabapentin. Third, measurements were conducted only at a single terminal time point, which re-

stricts the understanding of the temporal progression of vitamin D₃'s effects. Fourth, the use of the hot plate and manual von Frey filament tests, while non-invasive and free of chemical interference, may be influenced by variations in the animals' motor coordination following nerve injury. In addition, the relatively small sample size per group ($n = 4$) may limit the ability to capture biological variability, although the repeated-measures design partially reduces interanimal variability. Finally, TRPV1 expression was significantly associated with inflammatory cell infiltration and pain-related behaviors; however, further mechanistic studies are required to establish causality.

Conclusion

This study found that the combination of gabapentin and vitamin D₃ was associated with reduced thermal hyperalgesia in the CCI rat model of neuropathic pain. This effect may be related to modulation of TRPV1 receptor expression in Schwann cells. These findings suggest that vitamin D₃ could serve as a potential adjuvant to gabapentin therapy; however, additional studies are required to confirm its efficacy and clarify the underlying mechanisms.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank Moh. Samsudin for his assistance with animal handling and Ayundya for her assistance with immunohistochemistry preparation.

References

- Alles SRA, Smith PA (2018) Etiology and pharmacology of neuropathic pain. *Pharmacological Reviews* 70: 315–347. <https://doi.org/10.1124/pr.117.014399>
- Alvarado AM, Aguilar Navarro S (2016) Clinical trial assessing the efficacy of gabapentin plus B complex (B1/B12) versus pregabalin for treating painful diabetic neuropathy. *Journal of Diabetes Research* 2016: e4078695. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/4078695>
- Baskozos G, Hébert HL, Pascal MM, Themistocleous AC, Macfarlane GJ, Wynick D, Bennett DL, Smith BH (2023) Epidemiology of neuropathic pain: An analysis of prevalence and associated factors in UK Biobank. *PAIN Reports* 8: e1066. <https://doi.org/10.1097/pr9.0000000000001066>
- Bishop EL, Ismailova A, Dimeloe S, Hewison M, White JH (2021) Vitamin D and immune regulation: Antibacterial, Antiviral, Anti-Inflammatory. *JBMR Plus* 5: e10405. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm4.10405>
- Câmara CC, Araújo CV, de Sousa KKO, Brito GAC, Vale ML, Raposo RDS, Mendonça FE, Mietto BS, Martinez AMB, Oriá RB (2015) Gabapentin attenuates neuropathic pain and improves nerve myelination after chronic sciatic constriction in rats. *Neuroscience Letters* 607: 52–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2015.09.021>
- Cao B, Xu Q, Shi Y, Zhao R, Li H, Zheng J, Liu F, Wan Y, Wei B (2024) Pathology of pain and its implications for therapeutic interventions. *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy* 9: e155. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-024-01845-w>
- Castro A, Li Y, Raver C, Chandra R, Masri R, Lobo MK, Keller A (2017) Neuropathic pain after chronic nerve constriction may not correlate with chloride dysregulation in mouse trigeminal nucleus caudalis neurons. *Pain* 158: 1366–1372. <https://doi.org/10.1097/j.pain.0000000000000926>
- Chabas J-F, Stephan D, Marqueste T, Garcia S, Lavaut M-N, Nguyen C, Legre R, Khrestchatsky M, Decherchi P, Feron F (2013) Cholecalciferol (Vitamin D3) improves myelination and recovery after nerve injury. *PLoS ONE* 8: e65034. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0065034>
- Chaplan SR, Bach FW, Pogrel JW, Chung JM, Yaksh TL (1994) Quantitative assessment of tactile allodynia in the rat paw. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods* 53: 55–63. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0270\(94\)90144-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0270(94)90144-9)
- den Boer C, Dries L, Terluin B, van der Wouden JC, Blankenstein AH, van Wilgen CP, Lucassen P, van der Horst HE (2019) Central sensitization in chronic pain and medically unexplained symptom research: A systematic review of definitions, operationalizations and measurement instruments. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research* 117: 32–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychores.2018.12.010>

- Fijałkowski Ł, Sałat K, Podkowa A, Zaręba P, Nowaczyk A (2017) Potential role of selected antiepileptics used in neuropathic pain as human GABA transporter isoform 1 (GAT1) inhibitors-Molecular docking and pharmacodynamic studies. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 96: 362–372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejps.2016.10.004>
- Finnerup NB, Kuner R, Jensen TS (2021) Neuropathic Pain: From mechanisms to treatment. *Physiological Reviews* 101: 259–301. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.00045.2019>
- Frey E, Karney-Grobe S, Krolak T, Milbrandt J, DiAntonio A (2018) TRPV1 agonist, capsaicin, induces axon outgrowth after injury via Ca(2+)/PKA signaling. *eNeuro* 5. <https://doi.org/10.1523/eneuro.0095-18.2018>
- Freyhagen R, Baron R, Tölle T, Stemmler E, Gockel U, Stevens M, Maier C (2006) Screening of neuropathic pain components in patients with chronic back pain associated with nerve root compression: A prospective observational pilot study (MIPORT). *Journal of Current Medical Research and Opinion* 22: 529–537. <https://doi.org/10.1185/030079906x89874>
- Gao N, Li M, Wang W, Liu Z, Guo Y (2024) The dual role of TRPV1 in peripheral neuropathic pain: Pain switches caused by its sensitization or desensitization. *Frontiers in Molecular Neuroscience* 17: e1400118. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnmol.2024.1400118>
- Gendelman O, Itzhaki D, Makarov S, Bennun M, Amital H (2015) A randomized double-blind placebo-controlled study adding high dose vitamin D to analgesic regimens in patients with musculoskeletal pain. *Lupus* 24: 483–489. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961203314558676>
- Grüter T, Blusch A, Motte J, Sgodzai M, Bachir H, Klimas R, Ambrosius B, Gold R, Ellrichmann G, Pitarokoili K (2020) Immunomodulatory and anti-oxidative effect of the direct TRPV1 receptor agonist capsaicin on Schwann cells. *Journal of Neuroinflammation* 17: e145. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12974-020-01821-5>
- Guo S-H, Lin J-P, Huang L-E, Yang Y, Chen C-Q, Li N-N, Su M-Y, Zhao X, Zhu S-M, Yao Y-X (2019) Silencing of spinal Trpv1 attenuates neuropathic pain in rats by inhibiting CAMKII expression and ERK2 phosphorylation. *Scientific Reports* 9: e2769. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-39184-4>
- He DD, Gao Y, Wang S, Xie Z, Song XJ (2020) Systematic administration of B vitamins alleviates diabetic pain and inhibits associated expression of P2X3 and TRPV1 in dorsal root ganglion neurons and proinflammatory cytokines in spinal cord in rats. *Pain Research and Management* 2020: e3740162. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/3740162>
- IASP (2025) Neuropathic Pain. [accessed 13 August.2025] <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-443-10583-8.00037-4>
- Ismail A, Turchan A, Sudiana IK, Utomo B, Parenrengi MA, Suryaningtyas W (2024) Oral Gabapentin's effect on the expression of cytokines IL-6 and IL-10 in the dorsal column of spinal cord following experimental partial sciatic nerve ligation in rats. *Bali Medical Journal* 13: 1166–1169. <https://doi.org/10.15562/bmj.v13i3.5190>
- Jaggi AS, Jain V, Singh N (2011) Animal models of neuropathic pain. *Fundamental & Clinical Pharmacology* 25: 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-8206.2009.00801.x>
- Kaye AD, Armistead G, Amedio LS, Manthei ME, Ahmadzadeh S, Bernhardt B, Shekoohi S (2025) Evolving treatment strategies for neuropathic pain: A narrative review. *Medicina* 61: e1063. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina61061063>
- Konijeti GG, Arora P, Boylan MR, Song Y, Huang S, Harrell F, Newton-Cheh C, O'Neill D, Korzenik J, Wang TJ, Chan AT (2016) Vitamin D Supplementation modulates T cell-mediated immunity in humans: Results from a randomized control trial. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism* 101: 533–538. <https://doi.org/10.1210/jc.2015-3599>
- Li J, He J, Li H, Fan B-F, Liu B-T, Mao P, Jin Y, Cheng Z-Q, Zhang T-J, Zhong Z-F, Li S-J, Zhu S-N, Feng Y (2018) Proportion of neuropathic pain in the back region in chronic low back pain patients - a multicenter investigation. *Scientific Reports* 8: e16537. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-33832-x>
- Liu X, Nelson A, Wang X, Farid M, Gunji Y, Ikari J, Iwasawa S, Basma H, Feghali-Bostwick C, Rennard SI (2014) Vitamin D modulates prostaglandin E2 synthesis and degradation in human lung fibroblasts. *American Journal of Respiratory Cell and Molecular Biology* 50: 40–50. <https://doi.org/10.1165/rcmb.2013-0211OC>
- Long W, Fatehi M, Soni S, Panigrahi R, Philippaert K, Yu Y, Kelly R, Boonen B, Barr A, Golec D, Campbell SA, Ondrusova K, Hubert M, Baldwin T, Lemieux MJ, Light PE (2020) Vitamin D is an endogenous partial agonist of the transient receptor potential vanilloid 1 channel. *The Journal of Physiology* 598: 4321–4338. <https://doi.org/10.1113/JP279961>
- Malek N, Pajak A, Kolosowska N, Kucharczyk M, Starowicz K (2015) The importance of TRPV1-sensitisation factors for the development of neuropathic pain. *Molecular and Cellular Neuroscience* 65: 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcn.2015.02.001>
- Poisbeau P, Aouad M, Gazzo G, Lacaud A, Kemmel V, Landel V, Lelievre V, Feron F (2019) Cholecalciferol (Vitamin D(3)) reduces rat neuropathic pain by modulating opioid signaling. *Molecular Neurobiology* 56: 7208–7221. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12035-019-1582-6>
- Reyes-García G, Caram-Salas NL, Medina-Santillán R, Granados-Soto V (2004) Oral administration of B vitamins increases the antiallodynic effect of gabapentin in the rat. *Proceedings of the Western Pharmacology Society* 47: 76–79.
- Rusciano D (2024) Molecular mechanisms and therapeutic potential of gabapentin with a focus on topical formulations to treat ocular surface diseases. *Pharmaceuticals* 17: e623. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph17050623>
- Sari A, Akdoğan Altun Z, Arifoglu Karaman C, Bilir Kaya B, Durmus B (2020) Does vitamin D affect diabetic neuropathic pain and balance? *Journal of Pain Research* 13: 171–179. <https://doi.org/10.2147/jpr.S203176>
- Schober P, Boer C, Schwarte LA (2018) Correlation coefficients: Appropriate use and interpretation. *Anesthesia & Analgesia* 126: 1763–1768. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ane.0000000000002864>
- Shipton EA, Shipton EE (2015) Vitamin D and pain: Vitamin D and its role in the aetiology and maintenance of chronic pain states and associated comorbidities. *Pain Research and Treatment* 2015: e904967. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/904967>
- Thacker MA, Clark AK, Marchand F, McMahon SB (2007) Pathophysiology of peripheral neuropathic pain: immune cells and molecules. *Anesthesia & Analgesia* 105: 838–847. <https://doi.org/10.1213/01.ane.0000275190.42912.37>
- Tu WZ, Cheng RD, Cheng B, Lu J, Cao F, Lin HY, Jiang YX, Wang JZ, Chen H, Jiang SH (2012) Analgesic effect of electroacupuncture on chronic neuropathic pain mediated by P2X3 receptors in rat dorsal root ganglion neurons. *Neurochemistry International* 60: 379–386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuint.2012.01.006>
- Wang Q, He Y, Shen Y, Zhang Q, Chen D, Zuo C, Qin J, Wang H, Wang J, Yu Y (2014) Vitamin D inhibits COX-2 expression and inflammatory response by targeting thioesterase superfamily member 4. *Journal of*

- Biological Chemistry 289: 11681–11694. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M113.517581>
- Wiffen PJ, Derry S, Bell RF, Rice AS, Tölle TR, Phillips T, Moore RA (2017) Gabapentin for chronic neuropathic pain in adults. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews 6: Cd007938. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD007938.pub4>
- Xiaohua G, Dongdong L, Xiaoting N, Shuoping C, Feixia S, Huajun Y, Qi Z, Zimiao C (2021) Severe vitamin D deficiency is associated with increased expression of inflammatory cytokines in painful diabetic peripheral neuropathy. *Frontiers in Nutrition* 8: e612068. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2021.612068>
- Yamaguchi K, Kumakura S, Someya A, Iseki M, Inada E, Nagaoka I (2017) Anti-inflammatory actions of gabapentin and pregabalin on the substance P-induced mitogen-activated protein kinase activation in U373 MG human glioblastoma astrocytoma cells. *Molecular Medicine Reports* 16: 6109–6115. <https://doi.org/10.3892/mmr.2017.7368>
- Zakir HM, Mostafeezur RM, Suzuki A, Hitomi S, Suzuki I, Maeda T, Seo K, Yamada Y, Yamamura K, Lev S, Binshtok AM, Iwata K, Kitagawa J (2012) Expression of TRPV1 channels after nerve injury provides an essential delivery tool for neuropathic pain attenuation. *PLoS ONE* 7: e44023. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0044023>

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: Animal procedures were approved by the Ethics Committee of Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Airlangga No. 243/EC/KEPK/FKUA/2023.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

Regarding the use of AI in the preparation of this manuscript, the authors declare the following:

Artificial intelligence (ChatGPT) was used solely to assist with language refinement and clarity in parts of the manuscript. It did not generate scientific ideas, perform data analysis, or influence the study's results or conclusions. All AI-assisted text was reviewed and edited by the authors to ensure accuracy and appropriateness.

Funding

This study was financially supported by RKAT LPPM Universitas Airlangga under the SATU Joint Research Scheme (JRS) 2023 (Grant No. 1584/UN3.LPPM/PT.01.03/2023).

Author contributions

d'Arqom A contributed to concept development, idea formulation, definition of intellectual content, literature search, experimental studies, data acquisition, data analysis, statistical analysis, and draft preparation. Supriyanto HM contributed to concept development, literature search, design, experimental studies, data acquisition, data analysis, statistical analysis, manuscript editing, and manuscript review. Fillah AM contributed to the study design, experimental studies, data acquisition, manuscript editing, and manuscript review. Qorib MF contributed to the study design, experimental studies, data acquisition, manuscript editing, and manuscript review. Rimbun R contributed to the study design, data analysis, manuscript editing, and manuscript review. Lee MT contributed to the study design, manuscript editing, and manuscript review. Kadir SZSA contributed to the study design, manuscript editing, and manuscript review. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

Author ORCIDiDs

A. d'Arqom <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5412-9913>
 H.M. Supriyanto <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7054-5805>
 A.M. Fillah <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-7924-4620>
 M.F. Qorib <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4600-6649>
 Rimbun <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8283-7696>
 M.T. Lee <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3957-2439>
 S.Z.S.A. Kadir <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5593-2345>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.